

Participatory tools

SPEED BOAT

CLARIFY THE BIG IDEA TOGETHER: AGREE ON THE IDEA

How to ensure clarity of the goals (of the project) for everyone?

Each participant has their professional vocabulary or language (especially if participants are from different countries or disciplines) and their own cultural and personal representations. Thus, each person understands and receives information differently. This potentially leads to discrepancies between the information transmitted by the facilitator and the information that is understood.

Ensuring a shared, deep understanding (challenges, objectives, methods, roles) before launching the co-innovation project helps avoid tensions or even the failure of certain actions. Figure 6 illustrates how easy it is to create misunderstandings when you communicate.

How to solve it

To do this, you give each actor the opportunity to:

- Express themselves to explain things in their own way
- Participate from the beginning of the project whenever it is possible.

Source: Concevoir et animer une action de conseil collectif, Idele, 2005

Figure 1 Communication - a risky process

This way, you can ensure that all actors have the same objectives and clearly understand their tasks. If necessary, the objectives and tasks can be clarified and adjusted before the project starts. You will continue to ensure the clarity of the aims during the project.

When partners are involved later in the design process and not from the beginning, be sure everything is clear for them and take the time to question them about points you can adapt.

Word of advice

The actors need to share a common definition of key terms. Even if the term seems obvious, it costs nothing to agree on an understanding, which avoids confusion and loss of time during the project.

One example of a tool to facilitate this stage

Speed boat - Staying the course together

Description of the tool

- **What:** By visualising a boat sailing towards an island, we work on the group's objectives and what must be put in place to achieve them. The strengths, weaknesses, and milestones of the project are discussed. It can be used to plan, start a project, or make a mid-term assessment.
- **How long:** 45 minutes to 1h30
- **How many:** 10
- **What you'll need:**
 - Drawing on a flip chart or projecting a slide:
 - Place a boat in one corner and a treasure island in the other (see Fig. 7)
 - Visualise the wind in the sails/carrying currents = forces
 - Placing anchors/shark fins = weaknesses and risks
 - Moreover, sticky notes and markers

Steps:

- During the two first steps, each participant thinks about the different themes (objectives, strengths, obstacles and barriers). They then materialise

their ideas, position them on the visual medium (paper or digital), and explain them orally

- The first step aims to define the "Island", which is the projection of goals to be achieved: "In 3 years we will be...", "What will be different..."
- The second step is about strengths and weaknesses: "What helps/hinders us in achieving these objectives?"
 - The wind in the sails is the internal force of the group, the project.
 - The current near the boat represents the opportunities.
 - The anchors are the internal weaknesses.
 - The shark fins illustrate the risks.
 - The positioning of ideas is done spontaneously. If a team member finds a hindrance particularly annoying, they will place the idea very low down at the anchors. On the other hand, if they consider that one of the team's strengths constitutes a real booster, they will position their idea very high up in the space that represents the wind in the sails.
- At the end, the facilitator organises a debriefing of the exercise. The group validates the scheme and the milestones that have been set.

Testimony of the use

Manon Fuselier, IDELE, France

The objective of the Rhaporc project is to analyse the human-animal relationship in pig farming, its importance for the farmer, the animals and the results of the farm, and to propose ways for farmers to improve it. It is a national multi-actor project.

During this project, the speed boat tool was used to think collectively and identify hindrances and levers concerning the human-animal relationship. It also helped to bring out solutions. The facilitator gathered farmers and advisors (about 12).

During the interview, Manon Fuselier said, "This tool is very illustrative and very rich! It allows participants to develop their thinking through images. These images help in visualisation and allow many ideas to emerge. It is very rich despite the online format."

"When you look at the synthesis, you can see the link between each element; you can see what makes the boat move forward, what slows it down. The whole picture takes shape! It's very interesting!"

She also highlighted that "The most difficult thing was to make participants understand

where we wanted to take them. There were sometimes people who didn't understand what the image represented. Hence the importance of clarifying what each image means. You have to find the balance between the time to explain and the time to take action in order not to lose people."

Tips:

- This tool is accessible to beginners, but beware: it requires some preparation work for the facilitator
- During the introduction of the workshop, take the time to explain the instructions but don't forget to take action
- Adapt the elements around the boat to your question

